

Research Article

Beyond the Whiteboard: Transforming Lighting Education with Nur Mobile Lab

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Abstract: *Study of lighting is a fundamental component of building performance and key topic in Environmental Technology within Building Surveying education. As part of the early curriculum for students in built environment programs. As part of the early curriculum for students in built environment programs, this subject lays the groundwork for understanding building science concepts. However, conventional lecture-based delivery often limits student engagement and comprehension, especially in visualizing the seven principles of lighting. In response to this challenge, the Nur Mobile Lab was developed—an innovative, portable learning tool aligned with active and experiential learning approaches. Fabricated from lightweight plywood and acrylic Perspex, the device functions as a mobile lighting module equipped with a torchlight (as the artificial light source) and mist spray to visualize light behavior. This module enables students to physically explore lighting concepts beyond the limitations of static lectures and enhancing visual-spatial understanding. A study of student feedback from a structured questionnaire involving second-year Diploma in Building Surveying students demonstrated improved learning outcomes and engagement. Students reported that the ability to visualize lighting principles significantly deepened their understanding. This innovation supports current educational trends in integrating low-cost, mobile edtech solutions to facilitate blended and student-centered learning environments in technical and design-based programs.*

Keywords: visual education; lighting principles; mobile education unit.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Understanding basic lighting concepts is important for students in building science. It helps them think critically and apply knowledge in building surveying. However, many students struggle to understand lighting principles, especially in their first year of study. This is because they come from different school backgrounds and are still adjusting to university-level learning.

In the Environmental Technology subject for Diploma in Building Surveying, lighting is one of the key topics. Students must learn several basic theories related to lighting and how it affects building performance. For instance, students are expected to master abstract concepts such as light distribution, reflection, glare, and daylighting strategies. These theories are often conceptual and difficult to visualize. As a result, students find it hard to understand and apply them correctly.

To overcome the teaching challenges in lighting education, the Nur Mobile Lab was introduced as a portable and hands-on learning tool. It helps students connect theoretical lessons with real-world applications through visual and physical activities (Dong et al, 2024). The lab features a compact lighting box with interchangeable parts, allowing students to explore and observe how seven basic lighting principles work. A simple user manual guides them through each activity, encouraging independent learning both inside and outside the classroom.

This study examines how the Nur Mobile Lab affects student learning and engagement. Exam results from two academic semesters were compared to see if students improved in applying lighting concepts to problem-solving tasks. Additionally, a structured questionnaire was administered to gather qualitative feedback on students' experiences with the mobile lab. Preliminary findings indicate a marked increase in conceptual clarity, confidence, and enthusiasm for the subject.

By embedding modular and practical learning into the curriculum, the Nur Mobile Lab supports current trends in science and technology education. These trends focus on active learning, student participation, and real-world relevance. This innovation not only improves teaching methods but also helps prepare students with the knowledge and skills needed for the building industry (Robles-Moral, Fernandez-Diaz & Ayuso-Fernández, 2023).

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This innovation supports the learning outcomes of the Environmental Technology course, where students are expected to demonstrate their understanding of lighting design and perform basic lighting calculations. These skills help ensure sufficient lighting in indoor spaces, following the Malaysian Standard: Energy efficiency and use of renewable energy for non-residential buildings - Code of Practice (MS:1525, 2014). The Nur Mobile Lab encourages creative learning through hands-on classroom activities, helping students apply lighting principles in a practical and engaging way.

2.1 *The Innovation: Nur Mobile Lab Lighting Box*

The Nur Mobile Lab is a portable teaching tool designed to support lighting education. It consists of a rectangular box made from plywood and acrylic Perspex sheets, measuring 70 cm (L) × 50 cm (W) × 70 cm (H). The inside of the module is painted black to enhance lighting effects, while the transparent Perspex panels allow students to clearly observe demonstrations from outside. The module is lightweight and easy to assemble, making it suitable for assistance in various classroom or field settings. Inside, it is fitted with miniature furniture and materials that resemble a real room, helping students visualize how lighting principles apply in actual building spaces.

Additional components include a torchlight and laser pointer, which serve as light sources inside the box. A body mist spray is used to create a fogging effect, making the light rays more visible during demonstrations. These tools help illustrate the seven basic lighting principles in a hands-on and visual way. Figure 1 shows the updated version of the Nur Mobile Lab. In typical lecture sessions, these lighting principles are explained verbally, often supported by images or sketches. Figure 2 presents a visual overview of the seven lighting principles.

Figure 1. The updated version of the Nur Mobile Lab to demonstrate the seven lighting principles.

Figure 2. The theory of seven (7) lighting principles illustration.

2.2 Visual Demonstration of Lighting Principles

The Nur Mobile Lab was developed to help students better understand the seven key lighting principles taught in the environmental technology subject. These principles are essential for understanding how light behaves in building spaces. The seven principles include:

1. Solid angle (ω)
2. Luminous intensity (li)
3. Luminous flux (F)
4. Illuminance (E)
5. Inverse Square Law
6. Cosine law of illumination
7. Reflection (R)

Each principle has its own definition, unit of measurement, and formula that students must learn and apply.

1. Solid angle (ω)

The solid angle is defined as the portion of space enclosed by a cone with its tip at a point source, forming part of a sphere around that point. It represents how large an object appears to an observer at the source. The total solid angle around a point in a sphere equals the surface area divided by the square of the radius. The unit of measurement is the steradian (sr). Figure 3 shows how this principle is demonstrated using the Nur Mobile Lab.

Figure 3. Shows the demonstration of Solid Angle.

2. Luminous Intensity (I)

Luminous intensity refers to the amount of light emitted by a source in a specific direction. It is measured in candela (cd). Figure 4 shows the demonstration of luminous intensity.

Figure 4. Shows the demonstration of luminous intensity (I)

3. Luminous Flux (F)

Luminous flux is the total amount of visible light energy emitted by a source per unit of time. It represents the overall light output and is measured in lumens (lm). Figure 5 illustrates the concept of luminous flux

Figure 5. Shows the demonstration of luminous flux (F).

4. Illuminance (E)

Illuminance is the amount of luminous flux falling on a surface area. It indicates how well the surface is lit and is measured in lux (lx). Figure 6 shows the demonstration of illuminance

Figure 6. Shows the demonstration of illuminance(E).

5. Inverse Square Law (ISL)

The inverse square law explains how illuminance from a point light source decreases as the distance from the source increases. Specifically, illuminance is inversely proportional to the square of the distance. Figure 7 demonstrates the effect of the inverse square law.

Figure 7. Shows the demonstration of the inverse square law.

6. Cosine Law of Illumination (CLI)

The cosine law of illumination describes how the angle between the light source and the receiving surface affects the level of illumination. Tilting the surface reduces the effective illuminance based on the cosine of the angle. Figure 8 shows the tilting effect as described by the cosine law.

Figure 8. Shows the tilting effect of the Cosine Law of Illumination.

7. Reflection (R)

Reflection occurs when light changes direction after hitting the surface. There are two types of reflection:

- Specular reflection occurs on smooth surfaces, where light reflects in a single direction. The angle of incidence equals the angle of reflection. Figure 9 shows specular reflection.

Figure 9. Shows specular reflection on a smooth surface.

- Diffuse reflection happens on rough surfaces, scattering light in multiple directions. Figure 10 illustrates diffuse reflection.

Figure 10. Shows the demonstration of diffuse reflection on a rough surface.

3. FINDINGS

To assess the effectiveness of the Nur Mobile Lab video in improving student understanding of lighting principles, a structured questionnaire was administered to students who had recently completed the Environmental Technology subject. The survey included five key questions related to their comprehension, learning experience, and ability to visualize lighting concepts. Students were asked to rate their responses both before and after watching the demonstration video, using a five-point Likert scale.

The survey focused on several key areas: understanding the nature of light, grasping lighting principles and their measurements, overcoming difficulties in learning the topic, ability to memorize the principles, and overall impressions of the Nur Mobile Lab demonstration.

A total of 23 students participated in a feedback survey to evaluate the impact of the Nur Mobile Lab demonstration video on their understanding of lighting principles. The results showed a marked improvement across all five areas assessed. Before watching the video, most students rated their understanding of light and its nature as moderate or low. After viewing, the majority shifted to higher ratings, with many selecting “very” or “extremely.” Similarly, comprehension of lighting principles and measurement improved significantly, with 91% of students indicating that the video made the topic easier to understand. In terms of difficulty, responses prior to the video reflected moderate to high levels of struggle, whereas post-video responses showed reduced difficulty, with most students selecting “slightly” or “not at all.” Regarding memorization, 61% of students felt confident in recalling the seven lighting principles after watching the video, while 59% reported moderate confidence, acknowledging that memorization takes time. Finally, 96% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that the video helped them visualize and better understand lighting principles and their measurement. These results highlight the effectiveness of visual learning tools in enhancing student comprehension and engagement in technical subjects.

Figure 11. Result for understanding the Nature of Light.

Figure 12. The result for understanding the lighting principles and its measurement before and after watching the demonstration of the Nur Mobile Lab

Figure 13. The result on feedback of facing difficulty in understanding the lighting topic

Figure 14. The result of ability to memorize the topic before and after watching the demonstration.

Figure 15. The result on students' opinion in improving their understanding with the demonstration of the Nur Mobile Lab.

4. DISCUSSION

The feedback survey revealed strong positive responses toward the Nur Mobile Lab demonstration video as a learning aid for lighting principles. A significant majority of students (95%) reported improved understanding of the nature of light after watching the video, while 91% agreed that the video made it easier to grasp lighting principles and their measurement. Additionally, 78% of respondents indicated that the video helped reduce their difficulties in learning the topic. In terms of retention, 61% felt confident in memorizing the principles after viewing the demonstration, while 59% expressed moderate confidence, acknowledging that memorization requires time and repetition. Most notably, 96% of students agreed that the video enhanced their ability to visualize and comprehend lighting concepts more effectively. These findings suggest that integrating visual and interactive media—such as the Nur Mobile Lab—can significantly improve conceptual clarity, engagement, and retention in technical subjects like Environmental Technology.

5. CONCLUSION

The Nur Mobile Lab represents a practical and innovative approach to enhancing student understanding of lighting principles through visual learning aids. Designed as a lightweight and portable lighting box, it is easily deployed during classroom sessions to support instruction on artificial lighting topics within the Environmental Technology curriculum. Its mobility and simplicity make it suitable for broader educational use, including introductory lessons at the primary and secondary school levels. This mobile lab effectively addresses common student challenges in visualizing conceptual lighting concepts, offering a visible and interactive experience that reinforces theoretical knowledge. Similarly, Robles-Moral et al. (2023) emphasized the value of physical and digital models in supporting conceptual understanding in science education. The positive feedback of its video-based demonstration underscores the growing importance of visual learning strategies in technical education. Furthermore, the relevance of lighting education is supported by national standards such as Malaysian Standard: Energy efficiency and use of renewable energy for non-residential buildings -Code of Practice (MS1525:2014), which emphasizes the role of lighting in building performance and occupant well-being. The Nur Mobile Lab aligns with these standards by promoting awareness and understanding of lighting principles in a structured, student-friendly format.

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References

- Department of Standards Malaysia. (2014). *Malaysian Standard: Energy efficiency and use of renewable energy for non-residential buildings -Code of Practice (Second revision)*, MS1525:2014
- Dong, Z., Chiu, M. M., Zhou, S., & Zhang, Z. (2024). The Effect of Mobile Learning on School-Aged Students' Science Achievement: A Meta-analysis. *Education and Information Technologies*, 29, 517–544.
- Robles-Moral, F. J., Fernández-Díaz, M., & Ayuso-Fernández, G. E. (2023). A Study of the Usefulness of Physical Models and Digital Models for Teaching Science to Prospective Primary School Teachers. *Education Sciences*, 13(4), 343. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13040343>